

HORIZON 2020 - Coordination and Support Action

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**EU-PolarNet 2 - Co-ordinating and Co-designing the
European Polar Research Area**

Deliverable No. D 5.1

Implementation of the EU-PolarNet 2 website

Submission of Deliverable

Document information	
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Implementation of the EU-PolarNet 2 website

The address of the newly set up EU-PolarNet 2 website is www.eu-polarnet.eu. The domain was transferred from the previous host of the EU-PolarNet website to a new host (WordPress).